

ECO-FRIENDLY MANAGEMENT OF COOLING LUBRICANTS IN CNC MACHINES

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper aims to present the environmental and ecological benefits as a case study on sustainable technical solutions used CNC cooling lubricants, with lifetime extension and cooling quality increase.*

Methodology/approach – *Implementing modern treatment methods such as reverse osmosis, seeking to increase the quantity and quality of recovered water while reducing environmental impact, and additionally, installing a waste briquetting press and an extra filtration system to improve waste lubricant reuse and quality ratio.*

Findings – *A tested system for increasing the quality of recycled lubricants was successfully implemented.*

Research limitations/implications – *The specific application depends on the catted materials and the lubricant increased lifetime depends on lubricant and compliance with the proposed procedure parameters. The reduction of waste amount and the capability to be reused in the process, depends on the adopted devices.*

Practical implications – *The drawn conclusions are based on a specific industrial configuration and may be different if variables as working conditions are changed or if other machine configurations are chosen. Further research can be done to validate practices in other processing environments.*

Originality/value – *The study is developed and tested in real-world settings and may serve as a best practice guide for increasing lubricant quality and lifetime.*

Key words: *CNC machining, Cooling lubricants reuse, Ecological sustainable practices*

Introduction in Cooling Lubricants

The current industrial environment is radically transforming on two directions, which will affect all aspects of consumption and production in the 21st century: the entry into the fourth industrial age and the implementation of sustainable production methods (Abubakr, et al. 2020).

One of the imperative goals of today's manufacturing sector is the implementation of sustainable practices that ensure waste reduction and optimization of processing operations (Bastas 2021). Both the optimization of machining parameters, the operation of CNC machine sharpening tools (Mohsen, et al. 2024) and the extension of cooling lubricant life are in a mutual interdependence, jointly contributing to cost efficiency, machine life extension, and environmental sustainability.

According to the considered implemented internal procedures, the cooling lubricants used in CNC machining processes are of type B-Cool 755, manufacturer Blaser Swisslube AG, following safety specifications according to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH), Annex II, as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) No 2020/878 - Romania, the products being compatible with the European Directives 2015/863/EC, 2011/65/EC, 2002/95/EC, 2002/96/EC, WEEE, 2003/11/EC, 2005/53/EC and RoHS, and must not exceed 12 months from the date of manufacture mentioned on the accompanying documents.

The conformity in house is coordinated by the fluid mechanics Chief Mechanic, having responsibility for the entire chain of checking from reception, labelling, storage, use, condition monitoring, treatment, waste collection, stock management.

Therefore, the use of the cooling lubricant in the machining processes is done in strict compliance with the specified intervals in the product technical data sheet (24 months from the date of manufacture), respecting the FEFO system (first expired, first out).

For the best results, the manufacturer recommends a lubricant concentration in water between 4-15%. From our research, considering the techno-economic analysis, the lubricant concentration target value in the CNC pool for machining is to be set in the range (7-9) %. In the chipping processes, the cooling lubricant is lost on the resulting chip and evaporation, therefore the lubricant quantity is checked at each change and top up the required amount, monitoring and recording the following values: amount of lubricant topped up, the concentration of the topped-up lubricant, the lubricant quantity in the machine tank, water PH, water hardness and the quantity of nitrite. The cooling-hardening lubricant is maintained at $21\pm 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ with heat exchangers.

Reducing the environmental impact of cooling lubricant in CNC

Knowledge of the various types of cooling fluids and methods to make their use more efficient is extremely important to make these sustainability measures viable in long term (Shaikh and Ali 2021), as cooling and lubrication are critical aspects when discussing the smooth operation of machinery (Kumar, et al. 2023).

In terms of the environmental impact on the cooling lubricant, it is acted upon two directions of process analysis and improvement:

1. Increasing the lifetime of the cooling lubricant
 - a. Improving water quality by installing a reverse osmosis plant
 - b. Improvement of lubricant quality by additional by-pass filtration with centrifugal filtration stations
 - c. Daily monitoring of lubricant concentration and quality.
2. Sustainable solutions for reuse of cooling lubricant in the CNC machining process
 - a. Installation of a waste lubricant treatment plant
 - b. Installation of a briquetting press for aluminum alloy chips from CNC milling processes

The research, followed by the implementation was carried out following the five described steps, made in parallel for the two directions.

1.a Improving water quality by installing a reverse osmosis station

Initial situation: on the plant location the analyses carried out by an authorized laboratory, for the quality of the water used in the chipping processes showed a very high degree of hardness (14 dH), i.e. a level 3 hardness (>14 dH, total hardness >2.5mmol/l), is leading to a high risk of: high calcium deposits in the lubricant tanks, partial clogging of the cooling installations, impaired operation and a reduction in the lifetime of the tools fitted with lubricant cooling channels. For this reason, it was decided to install a reverse osmosis station.

In the initial standard conditions, the lubricant service life was only three months, followed by a complete cleaning of the lubricant basins also using bacteria removal solutions. Once determined the yearly requirement of cooling-lubricant for the entire workshop, the idea of a reverse osmosis station came up in order to create a deep filtration and separate the water for the lubricant solution. The schematic principle of operation is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Working principle of the reverse osmosis station (source: Gruenbeck Wasseraufbereitung)

After analyzing different solutions and catalogs with different products specifications and characteristics, the final decision was upon a system type GENO-OSMO MSR-750, manufacturer Gruenbeck, that may offer a maximum processing capacity of 750l/h.

The core system consists of a water treatment installation that on its turn consists of three installations: the filtration plant, the softening plant and the reverse osmosis plant. The schematic diagram of the water treatment installation is shown in Figure 2.

- Legend:
- A. GENOr-pur fine filter;
 - B. Euro system separator DK 2;
 - C. Geno-matr duo WE softening system O. GSX I soft water monitor;
 - D. Water analyses automat GENOr-control SP;
 - E. AKF activated carbon filter;
 - F. Fine filter 5um;
 - G. GENOr-OSMO-MSR; H Permeate filter;
 - I. Pressure boosting system

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the reverse osmosis plant (source: Gruenbeck Wasseraufbereitung)

In this configuration, the operation of the water plant implies that the reverse osmosis plant to be serviced annually, based on the service sheet that is as shown in figure 3.

Reverse Osmosis Inspection Sheet		
1.MEASURING VALUES		
Raw water pressure (bar.)	2	
Working pressure (bar.) HP pump	7	
Filter pressure drop check 5um	√	
Inlet water hardness measurement (*dH)	°dH	∅
Pressure pump current measurement	A	IR=2.8A; IS=2.8A; IT=2.9A
2.INSPECTION/VERIFICATION OF CONTROLLER AND SUB-ASSEMBLIES		
Check controller values/settings	√	Working Hours 34160
Check permeate, concentrate and recycling meter	m2	Σf=26394; Σk=17005; Σr=26816
Conductivity measurements	μS/cm	ECin=470μS/cm / ECPE=1μS/cm
Water temperature measurements	°C	t= 17°C
Percentage retention of soluble substances	%	R=99.99
Check/assess osmosis membrane status	√	replaced membranes, various r.
Flow rates Production	l/h	P=780; K=556; R=708
Checking mechanical tightness	√	
Check operating hours	√	M=60%
3. PERMEATE TANK		
Level sensor check	√	Replaced 3x BR390/50 Level sensor
Check ventilation valves	√	
Operational check	√	
4.CONNECTIONS, HOSES AND SEALS		
Checking seals	√	

Figure 3. Reverse osmosis plant annual overhaul report

1.b Lubricant quality improvement

An important aspect in machinery operation, is increased attention to the cooling-lubrication quality part, as a superficial approach can lead to production defects (Noor, et al.).

The recovered cooling lubricant quality may be improved and thus increases its service life in optimal conditions. The improved quality was obtained through an additional filtration of a bypass system with centrifugal filtration stations. After analyzing different types of products, a

centrifugal filtration station type Alfie 500, from Alfa Laval manufacturer, was selected for connection. The filtration capacity of the station is of maximum of 500 l/hour.

The application procedure was determined after several series of measurements, the optimal version being considered by connecting the filtration station in by-pass mode for 7 hours at each CNC, identifying that the maximum capacity of the CNC lubricant tanks is of about 750l. By centrifugal filtration at 7500 rpm, the station is able to filter oils and fine solid particles with the help of the conical disc set, the filtered oil being collected in a 20l capacity containers, equipped with a sensor for stopping the filtration when the maximum level is reached. The principle of operation of the centrifugal filtration station is also depicted in figure 4.

Figure 4. Working principle of the centrifugal filtration station (source: Alfa Laval)

Dirty liquid continuously enters at (A) and flows into the bowl (1). The bowl rotates at high-speed generating powerful centrifugal forces. As the liquid rotates with bowl, the liquid (heavy phase) and solid particles moves towards the periphery of the bowl. The particles (2) are deposited on the bowl wall, while the cleaned liquid enters the channels (3) and leaves the bowl at (B) at a constant pressure. The discs (4) in the bowl improves the cleaning efficiency during the separation process.

The oil (light phase) is forced towards the center of the bowl and then leaves through the underside of the bowl at (C).

1.c Daily monitoring of lubricant concentration and quality

Daily monitoring leads to identify and eliminate the elements that may influence the minimal consumption of lubricants during the normal cutting roves. The average daily quantity of cooling lubricant filled in the CNC machine-tools is about 150l. This quantity is generally lost through the resulting processing chips and evaporation.

The lubricant quantity is checked at each changeover and top up the required quantity, monitoring and recording the measured values like the quantity of lubricant topped up, the concentration of the topped-up lubricant and the lubricant in the machine tank, the water PH, water hardness and the quantity of nitrite.

The lubricant basins are equipped with level sensors, which indicate the maximum level, the warning level required to complete the lubricant and the minimum level when the CNC machine stops. The monthly monitoring of the amount of lubricant filled in relation to the number of hours produced is as shown in Figure 5.

		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	YTM
Cooling lubricant cumulated consumption	2022	5,824	10,816	18,304	22,464	27,872	32,448	37,856	44,096	49,920	55,328	60,320	65,312	65,312
	2023	4,576	9,568	16,224	20,800	27,456	32,864	38,272	42,432	44,712	48,040	48,872	48,872	48,872
	2024	4,576	7,072	8,736	10,608	12,272								
Production cumulated hours	2022	16,258	33,684	53,778	68,165	87,169	104,434	121,482	140,278	158,596	174,575	194,835	211,818	211,818
	2023	18,609	35,565	57,551	72,702	90,894	106,452	125,164	143,617	164,077	185,343	207,829	226,065	226,065
	2024	21,269	44,934	69,371	94,682	117,684								117,684
Cooling lubricant (liters) / Production hours	2022	0.36	0.32	0.34	0.33	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.31
	2023	0.25	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.30	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.27	0.26	0.24	0.22	0.22
	2024	0.22	0.16	0.13	0.11	0.10								0.10

Figure 5. Monthly monitoring of lubricant consumption in relation to the number of production hours

But after designing and installing the required devices, the new monitoring and management process begins for the entire workshop of forty-five CNC machine tools. Once the system is installed, a reduction in the number of bacteria, germs, particles and other organic compounds has been recorded, and after 3 years of monitoring, a real and positive impact on the environment is observed, with a reduction of 200 tons of lubricant waste being sent to an external recycling company.

2.a Installation of a waste lubricant treatment plant

Re-use of materials in manufacturing involves finding a new use for materials after they have served their original purpose, and making every effort to avoid producing waste (Noor, et al.)

The sustainable solutions for the reuse of cooling lubricant within the machining processes was the installation of a used lubricant treatment plant.

According to the data collected over a ten-year period, the average annual amount of used lubricant waste sent to an external recycling company is 200 tons. Considering the maximum amount of waste lubricants produced in one year (320 tons), sustainable solutions were sought. According to the legislation in this field (law 211/2011, article 43) and with the environmental audit, it is mandatory to implement clear solutions for the prevention and the reduction of the amount of waste generated in the production activities.

According to the European legislation (law 851/ 2015, article 9), the amount of hazardous waste must be reduced by finding sustainable solutions and reuse the materials in industrial processes. The considered technical solution, and also implemented, treats the lubricant waste (vacudest vacuum distillation system) by a process of evaporation under negative pressure at 85°C, followed by a return to atmospheric pressure, and vaporization at 120°C. As a result of the lubricant residue distillation treatment process, a residue concentrates (max. 5%) and industrial water (min.95%) is obtained and reused into production (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Distillation treatment of cooling lubricant waste (source: H2O GmbH))

The annual results show that the installation of the lubricant waste treatment plant reduces the amount of lubricant waste by 180 tons (95%) and the resulting water from the treatment is fully reused in the processing processes by extrusion, being mixed in a proportion of 20/80 with the water obtained from the reverse osmosis plant.

The lubricant waste treatment plant is fully automated, ensuring a high technical availability (>99%). The principal scheme is as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Principle diagram of the lubricant waste distillation treatment plant (source: H2O GmbH)

2.b Installation of a briquetting press for aluminum alloy scrap

From the CNC milling processes, the values recorded over a three-year period show an average annual quantity of 1800 tons of wet aluminum alloy scrap, with a 30% moisture content (lubricant residue) which led to a sustainable solution of installing a hydraulic scrap briquetting press (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Hydraulic press for briquetting aluminum alloy scrap (source: RUF Brikettiersysteme)

The system also operates in a fully automatic mode, with a loading area for the chip containers, screw conveyors that loads the pre-compression area, compression area ($P_{max}=30$ MPar) which provides 330 cylindrical briquettes/h, with maximum humidity of 5%.

The average quantity of lubricant recovered annually from the briquetting process is 33 tons of aluminum, the entire quantity being reused within new CNC milling processes.

An analysis report, issued by an analysis laboratory authorized by the producer of the cooling lubricant, is requested. Therefore, to ensure the quality of the processed used lubricant, a quality analysis is made prior to the reintroduction within the machining processes, (Figure 9).

To remove the amount of magnesium resulting from the briquetting process (49 mg/l), as is also shown in the analysis report, an additional lubricant filtration system was installed (Figure 10). The initial filtration is carried out with a roll filter with a filtration degree of $100\mu\text{m}$, for the final filtration being used two other filter cartridges with a filtration degree of $20\mu\text{m}$.

	Target range	Current	Previous samples	Method
Sample no.		23CH491423		
Art. no.		11755-03		
Sampling date		28.08.2023		
Overall assessment				
Concentration refractometer [%] *		7.6		FE.120.PA
pH value	8.7 - 9.3	9.4		FE.141.PA
pH value on-site		9.2		-
Color		gray		CS.115.STM
Odor sample		normal		CS.108.STM
Separation layer [%]	≤ 2	none		CS.118.STM
Average droplet size [µm]	≤ 0.700	0.189		CS.129.STG
Condition of emulsion		fine dispersion		CS.129.STG
Spec. conductivity [mS/cm]	≤ 7.0	3.1		FE.384.PA
Total hardness [°dH]	≤ 70	12		CS.130.STG
Magnesium [mg/l]		49		CS.135.STM
Chloride [mg/l]	≤ 150	7		CS.131.STG
Sulfate [mg/l]	≤ 400	5		CS.134.STM
Nitrite [mg/l]	≤ 20	0		CS.134.STM
Nitrate [mg/l]	≤ 150	1		CS.134.STM
HPTLC		carried out		CS.138.STM
Microbiology within tolerance?		not measured		CS.132.STG
Tramp oil [L/100L]		0.1		FE.413.PA
Other contaminations		not detectable		CS.138.STM

Figure 9 - Lubricant analysis bulletin resulting from the briquetting process

Figure 10 - Lubricant filtration system resulting from the briquetting process (source: BELKI teknik ApS)

Conclusions

In summary, the measures and objectives related to ecological, productivity and maintenance aspects have been met, as shown in Table 1, which presents the monthly monitoring, made for a period of over 3 years.

From a quantity of emulsion concentrate of 27872 liters (May 2022), the consumption has been reduced by 56%, to 12272 (May 2024), i.e. a reduction on a ramp-up of production hours by 35%, which also translates in a decrease in the quantity of lubricant by 68.8%, from 0.32l / production hour, to a current value of 0.10l / production hour.

The emulsion consumption per hour of production has been reduced by 68.8% through the use of the briquetting station and the increase in water quality. Through the filtration systems

and the installation of the reverse osmosis station, the emulsion lifetime was also increased from 3 to 12 months, resulting in a total monthly recovery of 75 cubic meters of water.

Table 1. Comparison Chart: Before/After implementation

Comparison: Initial vs. Actual Values			
Year	CLcc	PCh	CL/Ph (l/h)
2022 (Initial)	27872	87169	0.32
2024 (Actual)	12272	117682	0.1
+/-%	-56.0	35.0	-68.8
<i>Legend:</i>			
<i>CLcc</i>	<i>Cooling Lubricant cumulated Consumption (yearly value)</i>		
<i>PCh</i>	<i>Production Cumulated Hours (yearly value)</i>		
<i>CL/Ph (l/h)</i>	<i>Cooling Lubricant (liters) / Production hours (yearly value)</i>		

In terms of eco-friendly approach, the implemented project has achieved the desirable "6Rs" for sustainable production: Reduce, Reuse, Recover, Redesign, Remanufacturing and Recycling (Hegab, Kishawy and Darras 2019), all in accordance with Romanian and European waste management regulations.

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